

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF WEAR RESISTANCE OF CENTION-N AND ZIRCONOMER IN CLASS-I RESTORATION: AN IN-VITRO STUDY

SHAIMAA S. EL-DESOUKY*

Pediatric Dentistry, Oral Health, and Preventive Dentistry Department, Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt. *Corresponding Author Email: shaimaaeldesouky@dent.tanta.edu.eg

NANCY M. METWALLY

Pediatric Dentistry, Oral Health, and Preventive Dentistry Department, Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt. Email: nancy.mohamed@dent.tanta.edu.eg

EMAN A. E. SHEBL

Restorative Dentistry Department, Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt.
Email: eman_shebl@dent.tanta.edu.eg

REHAB F. GHOURABA

Oral Medicine, Periodontology, Oral Diagnosis, and Radiology Department, Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt. Email: rehab_gharabah@dent.tanta.edu.eg

IBRAHIM A. KABBASH

Public Health & Community Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, Tanta University Tanta, Egypt.
Email: Ibrahim.kabbash@med.tanta.edu.eg

SHIMAA M. HADWA

Pediatric Dentistry, Oral Health, and Preventive Dentistry Department, Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt. Email: shimaa.hadwa@dent.tanta.edu.eg

Abstract

Background: Direct restorative materials aim to use a strong, biocompatible substance that can adhere to the tooth structure indefinitely and has a respectably high wear resistance that is necessary to tolerate mechanical loads during bruxism and mastication. So, this research aimed to determine the resistance to wear of Cention-N compared to Zirconomer and Amalgam restorations in primary molar class I cavities.

Materials and methods: Three restorative materials, Cention – N, Zirconomer, and Amalgam, were utilized to prepare cavities in 90 human deciduous teeth that had been extracted. Using a chewing simulator, the restored teeth were subjected to mechanical and thermal stress, with a maximum of 1,200,000 load cycles. Using 3D scanning techniques, the abrasion area following the chewing simulation's termination was computed in addition to the number of cycles completed. **Results:** The Zirconomer group noticed a larger area of loss than the Cention-N and the Amalgam groups. The groups' differences were extremely statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) from each other using pairwise analysis using Tukey's Multiple Comparison Test. When the tooth type and loss area were compared, the first primary molars replaced with Zirconomer had the most loss, whereas the second primary molars restored with amalgam had the lowest loss. In the Cention-N and Zirconomer groups, the tooth type and the region of loss differed statistically significantly ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.004$, respectively). The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed a statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of the area of loss in the first and second primary molars ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Cention-N exhibits superior wear resistance and is a promising bioactive bulk fill resin composite restoration in the posterior region compared to Zirconomer. Cention N and amalgam were preferable restorative materials in stress-bearing areas compared to zirconomer, which had the least amount of wear resistance.

Keywords: Dental Restorative Material, Chewing Simulation, Class I Restoration, Wear Resistance.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most common chronic conditions that seems to be a global public health issue is dental caries [1]. Primary teeth with dental caries can be treated in a number of ways, from minimal intervention to restorative dentistry procedures [2]. Several factors may influence the longevity of primary teeth restorative materials including clinical variables, dental material properties, and operator skills [3].

Direct restorative materials in dentistry should be biocompatible and durable, binding to structure of the tooth, and have reasonably high resistance to wear, allowing them to sustain mechanical loads during bruxism and mastication [4]. Amalgam has been utilized in pediatric dentistry for many years; its cavity preparation is a more invasive approach due to the need for a retentive cavity design, leading to a significant destruction of hard tooth tissue [5]. Alternatively, tooth-colored restorations like glass-ionomer cements (GICs), composite, and compomer are used in pediatric dentistry to restore decayed primary teeth [6]. Resin-based composite is one of the most commonly utilized restorative materials because of its superior mechanical, aesthetic properties and good retention [7]. Nevertheless, it is considered to be technique-sensitive, costly, and time-consuming [8].

Glass-ionomer cement chemically bonds to dental hard tissues, releases fluoride, and is less technique-sensitive compared to adhesively bonded dental restorations [9]. On the other hand, conventional GICs have worse mechanical qualities with increased wear and breakage when applied to posterior teeth that bear loads [10]. Resin-modified glass-ionomer cement (RMGIC) has improved fracture and wear resistance, allowing for a higher clinical success rate [11]. However, these improvements, its weak mechanical properties, restricted suitability for stress-bearing areas, and poor aesthetic appeal caused to the need for alternative restorative materials [12].

It is important to find a genuine substitute for glass ionomer cement, silver amalgam, and composites which is an inexpensive, releasing fluoride, rapid and simple to utilize without the need for complex tools also, provide strength and good aesthetics [13]. Zirconia-infused GIC, known as Zirconomer, is a recent glass-ionomer restoration designed to overcome the challenges associated with conventional glass-ionomers with improved mechanical properties and enhanced aesthetics [14]. It is also reported to possess shear bonds strength comparable to amalgam and the fluoride-releasing ability like to that of traditional glass-ionomer cement.

Cention-N is a newly introduced a tooth-colored restorative material that is classified as an "alkasite", which has been recognized to be a composite material subgroup. It has an anti-cariogenic action by releasing calcium, hydroxyl, and fluoride ions [15]. Manufacturers of Cention-N matched the majority of its characteristics to those of GIC and amalgam. It was asserted that its ion-releasing qualities were similar to those of GIC and that its compressive strength and durability were equivalent to amalgam. Also, it is argued to be more translucent than GIC, making it superior in terms of aesthetics [16].

Primary and permanent teeth have varying abrasivities because of their distinct enamel strengths, morphological characteristics including dentin and enamel thickness, and the

different biting pressures used by adults and children accordingly, the primary teeth have lower wear resistance than permanent teeth [17]. According to Seghi et al. [18], the materials used for dental restorations should wear at rates equal to those of enamel surfaces. Wear resistance has been measured using a several of quantitative and qualitative techniques such as the Basic Erosive Wear Examination (BEWE) [19], Eccles [20], Smith and Knight [21], and the New Tooth Wear Index (NTWI) [22]. The primary drawback of these indicators is their subjectivity and inadequate sensitivity [23].

An early diagnosis is essential for managing this dental condition and preventing future loss of tooth or aesthetic problems. Since restorations must be resistant to form and structural changes without harming neighboring teeth, wear of dental materials is also crucial. So, the purpose of this study was to compare and assess the wear resistance of Cention-N, zirconomer restorative materials compared to Amalgam in class-I primary molars. The null hypothesis (H_0) assumed that there was not a difference in the wear resistance of Cention-N, a Zirconomer-reinforced glass ionomer, compared to that of the Amalgam restorations in Class I cavities in primary molars.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1. Study Setting and Ethical Consideration:

A comparative in-vitro study was carried out at the Department of Paediatric Dentistry, Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University, following approval from the ethical committee (REC), Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University (code #R-RD-9-24-3145) in accordance with the 1964 Helsinki Statement and subsequent amendments. Parents provided informed written consent to utilise their children's extracted teeth in the research.

2.2. Sample size calculation and randomization

The sample size calculation was performed using Epi-Info statistical software (developed by the World Health Organization and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, Georgia, USA, version 2002). The criteria for calculation included a 95% confidence level, 80% study power, and an anticipated clinical success rate of 60% in the least favorable treatment group versus 95% in the most favorable group. Based on these parameters, the required sample size per group was determined to be 23. To accommodate potential data loss and dropout rates, the sample size was increased to 30 primary mandibular molars per group.

Simple randomization was performed using the Research Randomizer software (<https://www.randomizer.org/>)[24]. A computer-generated randomization list was prepared by an independent individual, secured in a sealed and opaque wrapper, and used to assign participants meeting the inclusion criteria to one of the three groups.

2.3. Eligibility criteria

A total of 150 extracted primary mandibular molars due to ectopic eruption of permanent successors or serial extraction, were collected from the outpatient clinic of the Pediatric Dentistry Department at the Faculty of Dentistry, Tanta University. The chosen molars

were free of cusp wear, cracks, caries lesions, dental restorations, or any dental anomalies. Also, the included molars had intact enamel crown margins and at least one-third of the root. Severely worn-out, carious, or fractured teeth were excluded. Accordingly, sixty primary molars were excluded, yielding the final study sample of ninety children.

2.4. Teething groups

Ninety deciduous mandibular molars were randomly divided into three groups (30 molars each) based on restorative materials: (Table 1)

Group-I (experimental)(n=30): Sound primary mandibular molars were restored with Cention-N (Ivoclar Vivadent, Mumbai, India)

Group-II (experimental)(n=30): Sound primary mandibular molars were restored with Zirconomer Improved (Zirconia Reinforced Glass Ionome, Shofu, Kyoto, Japan)

Group-III (positive control) (n=30): Sound primary mandibular molars were restored with Amalgam SDI GS-80.

Table (1): The present study's materials, composition, and manufacturers

Materials	Composition	Manufacturers
Cention-N	Powder: Calcium-fluoro-silicate glass, Barium-Alumino-silicate glass, Ytterbium trifluoride, Isofiller (Copolymer), A copper salt & thiocarbamide-self cure Initiator or Ivocerin and acyl phosphine oxide-photoinitiator and Pigment Liquid: Urethane dimethacrylate (UDMA), Tetramethyl-xylylen diurethane dimethacrylate, Tricyclodecan-dimethanol dimethacrylate (DCP) Polyethylene glycol 400dimethacrylate (PEG-400 DMA), initiator (hydroperoxide – self-cure) and Stabilizer	Cention Ivoclar Vivadent, Mumbai, India
Zirconomer Improved	Powder: alumino-fluoro-silicate glass, zirconium ox-ide, tartaric acid Liquid: polyacrylic acid, deionized water	Shofu, Kyoto, Japan
Amalgam SDI GS-80 capsule	Ag 56% Sn 29%, Cu 15% Mercury	Made in Australia by SDI Limited Bayswater, Victoria 3153www.sdi.com.au

2.5. Tooth Specimen Preparation:

A total of 90 eligible mandibular primary molars were thoroughly cleaned to remove debris, blood, and soft tissue, followed by disinfection with a 0.1% thymol solution [25]. The teeth were then stored at 37 °C in deionized water (SIGALD, Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH) that was replaced weekly and kept for a maximum of one month before use [26]. Each molar was embedded in a standard acrylic resin mold (12 x 12 mm, Acrostone, Egypt), with the occlusal surface positioned upward and the root portion embedded up to 1 mm below the cemento-enamel junction [27].

2.6. Cavity preparation and restorations:

Class I cavities (4 x 2 x 1 mm deep) were prepared using no. 330 bur in the selected primary molars [28] with a single operator to guarantee uniform cavity preparation in terms of size and depth. To ensure uniformity, the cavity's dimensions were determined with a William's graduated periodontal probe. Then, teeth specimens were restored with tested restorative materials following the manufacturer's instructions. In Group-I (Cention-N group), a powder/liquid weight ratio of 4.6 to 1 was achieved by using one scoop of powder for every drop of liquid which was mixed manually to a smooth consistency [29].

The cavity was restored with a single increment of Cention-N and left to polymerize. Since it contains photo-initiators, additional light curing can be applied using blue light with a wavelength of approximately 400–500 nm. After curing, restorations were finished and polished.

In group-II (Zirconomer group), two scoops of powder, measured using the provided scoop, and a single drop of liquid were dispensed onto the mixing pad. [30] and mixed till a thick putty-like consistency was reached (a total of 30 seconds). Then the cavity was filled, finished, and polished. While in group-III (amalgam group), the amalgam capsule was activated and mixed in a capsule mixer according to the specifications.

Amalgam was manually condensed into the cavity preparation, ensuring coverage of all walls and cavo-surface margins. It was then carved to match the tooth contour using a sharp carver and the restorations were polished after 72 hours [31].

2.7. Wear Resistance test

For one week, all teeth samples were saved in distilled water at 37°C. The teeth were then subjected to 1000 thermal cycles in the thermocycling device (Thermocycler, SD Mechatronik, Feldkirchen-Westerham, Germany) between two water baths with temperatures ranging from 5° to 55°C, each with a 60-second stay time [32].

After thermocycling, the restored teeth were securely attached to specific holders before being mounted into multifunctional chewing simulator chambers (CS4, SD Mechatronik, Feldkirchen-Westerham, Germany). Each tooth specimen was positioned beneath a flat-planed polyacetal stylus with a diameter of 4.0 mm, which was mounted on a spring-loaded piston [33].

The experimental conditions of wear testing include a 3 mm vertical and a 2 mm horizontal motion. The masticatory force was determined based on findings from previous studies that assessed the abrasiveness of dental materials and primary teeth [32, 33]. In this study, a masticatory force of 50 N was selected, representing the midpoint between the lowest and highest forces reported in earlier research. To achieve the 50 N force, a 5 kg load was used to each chamber.

To replicate circumstances in the oral cavity, a loading cycle frequency of 0.8 Hz with a lateral sliding component of 0.3 mm towards the central fissure was selected. The descending and ascending velocities were both 55mm/s. Additionally, a thermodynamic environment resembling real oral conditions was simulated using a computer-controlled

hot/cold water circulation system [32]. This technique was performed for 250,000 cycles, which conveys to one year of artificial aging, with artificial saliva functioning as the chewing medium [34].

Following material testing, a CBCT scan (KaVo OP 3D Vision, Kavo Dental, Biberach, Germany) was performed with the smallest field of view (8D, 8Hcm) and fixed exposure parameters (120 Kv, 5 mA, and 0.125 mm voxel size) in order to enhance spatial resolution. The dental module of The On-Demand Dental software (Seoul, Korea, version 1.0, build 1.0.10.7510, x64 Edition) which allowed the superimposition of STL files obtained by the scanner (Helios 500, Changzhou Sifary, China) before and after testing the materials on DICOM images of CBCT allowing to measure the gap resulted after testing the materials as shown on figures (1, 2, 3).

Figure (1): (A) CBCT DICOM image of mandibular second primary molar restored with cention-N with superimposition of a pre-STL file (pink in color) and post-STL file (blue in color), the gap area was measured using the area tool of CBCT software. (B) a reconstructive 3-D view of CBCT after superimposition of STL files revealed a slight loss in cention-N restoration

Figure (2): (A) CBCT DICOM image of mandibular second primary molar restored with zirconomer with superimposition of a pre-STL file (pink in color) and post STL file (blue in color), the gap area was measured using the area tool of CBCT software. (B) A reconstructive 3-D view of CBCT after superimposition of STL files revealed a moderate loss in the zirconomer restoration

Figure (3): (A) CBCT DICOM image of mandibular second primary molar restored with amalgam with superimposition of a pre-STL file (pink in color) and post-STL file (blue in color) with no gap. (B) A reconstructive 3-D view of CBCT after superimposition of STL files revealed nearly no loss in amalgam restoration

2.8. Statistical analysis:

All data was collected, tabulated, and statistically analyzed. Also, it was provided as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) values. We utilized one-way ANOVAs for comparing the four study groups. Tukey's post hoc test was used to determine statistical significance among groups. Statistical significance was set as p-values < 0.05 .

3. RESULTS

The greater area of loss was observed in the Zirconomer group ($1.037 \pm 0.2330 \text{ mm}^2$) compared to $0.7916 \pm 0.1483 \text{ mm}^2$ in the Cention-N group and $0.03938 \pm 0.07690 \text{ mm}^2$ in amalgam group. There was a highly statistically significant difference among groups ($p < 0.001$) (Table-2) (Figures 1,2,3). Using pairwise analysis by Tukey's Multiple Comparison Test, each group was statistically highly significant from the other.

Table (2): Comparison of area of loss for all tested restorative materials

Measures of area of loss	Cention-N	Zirconomer	Amalgam
Mean \pm SD	0.792 \pm 0.148	1.037 \pm 0.233	0.039 \pm 0.077
F	295.6		
P	$< 0.001^{***}$		
#Pairwise analysis by Tukey's Multiple Comparison Test each group was significant from each other, M=Mean, SD: Standard Deviation			

By comparing the area of loss with the tooth type, the highest loss was found in the first primary molars restored with Zirconomer (1.06 ± 0.17) while the lowest loss was observed in the second primary molars restored with amalgam (0.02 ± 0.04) (Table-3). There was a

statistically significant difference between the area of loss and the tooth type in the cention-N and zirconomer groups ($p < 0.001$, $p = 0.004$ respectively). Regarding the area of loss in the first primary molars, there was a highly statistically significant difference among groups using the Kruskal-Wallis test ($p < 0.001$) also, a highly statistically significant difference was noted concerning the area of loss in the second primary molars ($p < 0.001$).

Table (3): Comparison of the area of loss for all tested restorative materials with the tooth type

Area of loss	Tooth		Z	p
	D	E		
Cention-N				
Range	0.80-1.00	0.45-0.79	4.666	<0.001
Mean+SD	0.91+0.07	0.67+0.10		
Zirconomer				
Range	0.66-1.44	0.69-2.00	2.884	0.004*
Mean+SD	1.06+0.17	1.02+0.29		
Amalgam				
Range	0.00-0.33	0.00-0.12	1.712	0.087
Mean+SD	0.06+0.11	0.02+0.04		
Kruskal-Wallis	34.471	39.605		
p	<0.001*	<0.001*		

4. DISCUSSION

Resistance to occlusal wear is a crucial factor for oral restorations to be clinically successful. The wear of restorative materials should be as comparable to natural enamel as feasible. So, perfect restorative material should withstand any difficulties that may arise in the oral cavity and cause the material to wear away. Furthermore, neither opposing natural teeth nor restorative materials should be abraded by a restorative material [35]. Thus, this study was directed to assess and compare the wear resistance of three restorative materials on Class-I primary molars.

The chewing simulator was used to test the materials' surface characteristics as it closely mimics the oral stresses and loaded the restorations. Wear simulation tools and techniques have been created because in vivo wear studies are difficult and time-consuming. Also, chewing simulators may replicate basic activities like grinding and clenching and offer identical circumstances for the material being tested during a wear test [36]. Moreover, the wear test conditions utilised in this study were revealed to be an effective in vitro approach to assessing clinical performance in children.

The loading force is an important component of an in-vitro wear test investigation. A 50 N loading force was used in the present study to imitate the conditions in a child's oral cavity, which is the average of the physiological biting forces in bruxism-free patients. Horizontal movement was also used in this test to replicate intraoral mastication. The number of 250,000 cycles in a chewing simulator, clinically corresponds to the number of chewing cycles per year for an individual; this corresponds to a pilot study by Jung et al., [37] in which wear was limited to primary tooth enamel and did not progress into dentin.

Simultaneous thermal cycling with water stimulates temperature variations in the oral cavity and eliminates wear particles produced during wear tests, stimulating aging [38].

The area of loss in this study showed a mean of $0.7916 \pm 0.1483 \text{ mm}^2$, $1.037 \pm 0.2330 \text{ mm}^2$, and $0.03938 \pm 0.0769 \text{ mm}^2$ in Cention-N, Zirconomer, and amalgam respectively. Zirconomer showed a statistically significantly higher mean compared to Cention-N and amalgam. Amalgam showed the highest wear resistance; this may be attributed to the metallurgically complex material which makes amalgam resistant to wear in the oral environment [39]. This agreed with Shrutika et al., [40] who reported the superior performance of amalgam with the least wear loss. Also, this was consistent with Chun et al., [41] who stated that the mechanical characteristics of dental restorative materials, such as amalgam, are comparable to or superior to those of dentin, and their hardness value is lower than that of enamel. Moreover, Rajih et al., [42] conclude that the hardness of amalgam filling grows over time, and the reason for this is the relatively slow reaction rate, which takes days or even weeks to complete.

In this study, Cention-N was significantly higher than zirconomer; this significant difference may be clarified by the presence of a highly cross-linked monomer network in Cention-N material, which produces a high degree of polymerization and appropriate mechanical properties through the use of a stable, efficient self-cure initiator and shrinkage stress reliever [43]. Additionally, the spherical shape of Cention-N filler particles allows for a greater filler load and boosts their compressive strength since mechanical stresses appear to concentrate on the angles and protuberances of the filler particles [44]. This agreed with Adsul et al., [45] who concluded that Cention-N is a promising restorative material with superior mechanical properties compared to Zirconomer.

Zirconomer showed a statistically significantly higher mean compared to Cention-N and amalgam in the current study; this agreed with the findings of Mohamed et al., [46] who compared Zirconomer[®]-Improved and EQUIA[®] Forte Fil restorations and found that Zirconomer[®] showed less resistance to wear. The manual mixing of Zirconomer[®] Improved material may be the cause of its poor performance since it introduces air bubbles into the matrix, which leads to surface hydrolytic instability and softening. Additionally, Zirconomer[®] Improved restorative material has areas of stress concentrations with subsequent material loss due to the absence of chemical bonding between the zirconia fillers and the polysalt matrix. Additionally, it exhibits greater elastic deformation and a lower elastic modulus. So, it deforms when exposed to functional loads [46]. Conversely, this is opposed by Shrutika et al., [40] who stated that zirconomer had the least amount of wear resistance compared to amalgam and Filtek Z350.

This study has some limitations. Although in vitro research give encouraging findings, clinical trials are required to determine the most appropriate restorative materials for primary teeth. This study's circumstances, masticatory movement, and occlusal force are different from those found in the oral environment. Further research is needed, particularly hardness testing, nano-hardness testing, enamel and dentin bond strength, and fracture resistance.

5. CONCLUSION

These conclusions are based on the results of this in vitro investigation.

- Cention-N is an encouraging bioactive bulk fill resin composite restoration in the posterior area with superior wear resistance compared to Zirconomer.
- Zirconomer showed the lowest wear resistance of the three tested restorative materials.
- According to present research Cention N and amalgam were found to be better restorative materials for use in stress-bearing areas.

Declarations

Ethical approval and consent to participate.

The ethical commission (REC) of Tanta University's Faculty of Dentistry granted ethical approval for this study, which complies with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments. The code for this approval is #R-RD-9-24-3145. At the time of extraction, the parents of the patients were told of the study's goal and provided their informed written consent.

Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets used and/or analysed in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing interests

Regarding this article, the authors revealed no relevant conflicts of interest.

Funding

The authors of this article did not get any financial assistance from any organisations.

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